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ASSESSMENT OF THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS WITH LUMBAR HERNIAS BEFORE AND AFTER DIFFERENTIATED SURGICAL TREATMENT

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Abstract

The article of data on the effectiveness of modern methods of treatment of intervertebral hernias of the lumbar spine is presented. Historical aspects of the development of spinal neurosurgery, the main methods of surgical treatment. This publication presents the main methods of surgical treatment of herniated intervertebral disc, characterizes the positive and negative aspects of each method. A differentiated approach to the treatment of intervertebral disc herniations in the lumbar spine. Assessment of quality of life and pain syndrome using questionnaires. Determining the effectiveness of surgical treatment and the impact on the quality of life of patients.

Keywords: diagnostics, herniated disc, surgical treatment, conservative treatment, differentiated an approach.

Relevance

Since ancient times, with the advent of man, his physical actions began to cause stress on the whole body, primarily on the organs of movement. The load fell on the legs, arms and spine, at that time the main food product was meat of animals and birds with a high calcium content. Subsequently, the gradual intake of other food products of plant origin with the invention of various devices facilitating human labor gradually began to appear signs of a sedentary lifestyle. In connection with the rapid development of urbanization and a decrease in physical activity of a person's inactivity, the first signs of the so-called osteochondrosis began to appear at present [6,11,12].

The causes of the appearance of a herniated disc according to literary data can be different in their origin due to inflammatory processes, physical activity, injury, and so on. Currently, in developed countries of the world, most often herniated discs appear due to inactivity and a sedentary lifestyle of people. According to world statistics, osteochondrosis with back pain affects a huge number of people - over 80% of the world's population [1,7,10]. Osteochondrosis with back pain, according to literary data, is quite common, in the population it makes up 58-84% of patients, and the incidence is 4-33% per year [1,4,7,12,10].

The incidence rates of osteochondrosis with back pain in different countries of the world may vary, the more developed the country, the more patients. With osteochondrosis of the spine, herniated discs are a common cause of lower back pain. In this case, lower back pain, localized in the back area, is limited from above

by the twelfth rib, and from below by the lower gluteal folds [6,7,12,20].

For example, according to literary data, the incidence of chronic back pain due to osteochondrosis of the spine among adults is determined to be 26–33% of the total number of neurological patients in the population [7,12,20].

At present, the issue of surgical tactics and differentiated approach to the treatment of intervertebral disc herniations at the level of the lumbar spine remains not fully resolved.

Depending on the method of treatment, further rehabilitation of patients depends. In some cases, when a fixing system is installed on the spine, the rehabilitation period may be extended due to long-term consolidation, and accordingly, the quality of life of patients suffers longer [3,4,5, 9,12,13,14,15,16,17].

At the current stage of development of medicine, since the active use of MRI and MSCT in the practice of neurosurgeons, it has become possible to assess various pathologies of the intervertebral disc pathology through radiation diagnostics. Subsequently, the use of electroneuromyography (ENGM) made it possible to determine the level of damage to the nerve root, making it possible to determine the tactics of surgical treatment [2,7,20].

Currently, the quality of life is assessed by various scales and questionnaires. For a full-fledged study of the quality of life of patients, it is of great importance to assess the overall quality of life, quality of life by disease and symptom of the disease [8,12,16].

Thus, the issue of differentiated surgical treatment of intervertebral disc herniations remains not fully resolved. Pain syndrome that occurs with intervertebral disc herniations sharply reduces the quality of life of patients.

Purpose of the study: to improve the treatment results of patients with lumbar spine herniations by using differentiated treatment tactics with an assessment of the quality of life.

Material and methods

The study is based on the results of observations of 165 patients with lumbar pain who were treated in the hospital of the Tashkent Medical Academy, a multidisciplinary clinic, and the neurosurgery department from 2019 to 2023.

To establish a diagnosis and choose a treatment method, all patients underwent a comprehensive examination, including clinical, neurological and instrumental research methods.

During the initial examination of patients, the main criteria for lumbar osteochondrosis (LO) were the presence of the following symptoms - unilateral or, in rare cases, bilateral pain in the lumbar region radiating to the leg; the presence of sensitivity disorders in the innervation zone of any roots of the lumbar vertebrae; the presence of symptoms such as hypertonicity of the lumbar muscles due to pain syndrome; limited movement due to pain syndrome or paresis of the limbs; atrophy of the leg muscles in the innervation zone of the roots of the lumbar vertebrae was also checked.

An important place in establishing a diagnosis and determining further treatment tactics was given to magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) data from 1.5 to 3.0 Tesla, MSCT and digital X-ray research methods.

In our studies, we used electroneuromyography (ENMG), which determines the level of damage to the roots of the equine tail, with a reliability of 75%, giving us the opportunity to choose the tactics of surgical or conservative treatment of lumbar pain syndrome in osteochondrosis of the spine.

In our studies, questionnaires were used to assess the quality of life of patients: the European Quality of Life Questionnaire Euro QoL-5D and a visual analogue scale (VAS) to determine the intensity of pain. After diagnosis, all patients were subjected to surgical intervention or conservative treatment by determining the tactics in principle of increasing radicality of pain syndrome and signs of damage to the roots.

Results and discussion

The results of observations of 165 patients with lumbar pain who were treated in the inpatient department of the Tashkent Medical Academy, a multidisciplinary clinic, and the neurosurgery department from 2019 to 2023 were studied.

All patients were divided into three groups according to treatment methods, severity of lumbar osteochondrosis pain syndrome, and somatic status.

The first group included 53 (32.2%) patients who underwent conservative treatment, blockades, physiotherapy, and other treatment methods. The second group included 55 (33.3%) patients who underwent endoscopic methods of removing a herniated disc between the 4-5 and 5-1 sacral vertebrae of the lumbar

spine. The third group consisted of 57 (34.5%) patients who underwent surgery to remove a herniated disc using intralaminar access.

By age, patients are distributed according to the WHO classification, which provides for the allocation of age groups: young age 14-19 years; younger middle age 20-44 years; older middle age 45-59 years; elderly age 60-74 years; old age 75-89 years; In our observations, patients were aged from 24 to 79 years.

Distribution of patients by age and gender showed that among the patients, men predominated, there were 116 (70.2%), and women - 49 (29.8%), which is associated with the physical exertion of men during work. The majority of patients 68 (41.5%) were older middle and old age, the maximum number of patients fell on the age group 60-74 years, 50 (30.4%), which is consistent with the data of world scientists.

Examination of the somatic status revealed that out of 165 patients, 67 (40.5%) had somatic pathology, manifested as arterial hypertension in 51 (31.0%) patients, ischemic heart disease in 13 patients (7.8%). Diabetes mellitus was noted in 18 (11.2%) observations, liver pathology in 4 (2.6%) patients and renal failure in 1 (0.9%). It should be noted that a combination of two or more somatic diseases was noted in the same patient, this was especially typical for cardiovascular diseases.

In our studies, 112 (67.8%) of 165 patients underwent surgical treatment, the indications for surgical treatment were: cauda equina syndrome with increasing dysfunction of the pelvic organs and radiculo-ischemic manifestations; duration of radicular pain syndrome or pain in the lumbar region for at least 4 weeks; intervertebral disc herniation of any localization, but only at one level, confirmed by MRI with axial sections; lack of effect from conservative treatment.

Neurological symptoms in the second and third groups in total 173 cases, they could combine several symptoms at once in one patient in both groups. The most frequent complaint presented by patients of the second and third groups was pain in the lumbar spine 38 cases, the second most frequent complaint was gait disturbance and sensory disturbance 36 cases each, the third most common complaint was a forced body position due to pain syndrome 27 cases.

Analysis of the level of damage to the roots of the equine tail in the studied 165 patients showed the following results, twice as much observation at the level of LV-SI 106 (64.3%) compared to LIV-LV 59 (35.7%) this is due to the greatest load on the lumbar spine associated with a low-mobility sacrum.

Positive results among the 165 patients studied were noted in 156 (95.6%), without changes in 9 (5.4%). The indicators in all 3 groups were good, since a differentiated approach to the treatment of patients with lumbar pain is always justified.

This proves the effectiveness of methods for treating patients with lumbar hernias with a differentiated approach.

The quality of life, study of 165 patients was achieved using the European Quality of Life Questionnaire EuroQoL-5D and a visual analogue scale (VAS) to determine the intensity of pain.

In all study groups, the parameters of the EuroQol-5D questionnaire such as pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression worsened the most. The study of the quality of life of patients in all groups was conducted before and after surgical treatment.

Analysis of the results of the quality of life (QOL) study of 165 patients showed that the data obtained in all three groups are different, the deterioration of the QOL indicators of the first group does not differ much from normal, in the second group it was revealed that the QOL indicators of patients moderately worsened, in the third group this indicator of QOL of patients worsened greatly and was slowly restored, this is due to the course of the disease and degenerative changes in osteochondrosis of the spine with concomitant somatic pathology.

The pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression descriptors were deviated from the norm to a greater extent in the second and third groups and were slowly restored, the QOL indicators of the patients of the first group returned to normal immediately after surgical treatment.

A study of 165 patients showed that the QOL parameters pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression suffer the most, this is facilitated by the emotional state of patients.

Pain syndrome as a strong irritant primarily affects the emotional state of patients, being a provoking factor in the deterioration of the QOL of patients.

For a full assessment of the QOL of patients, it is necessary to use two or more questionnaires covering more impaired descriptors and indicators. To study the parameters of pain syndrome, we used a scale (VAS) for the completeness of the study.

VAS scores before surgery revealed mild pain (1-3 points) in 20 (37.7%) patients in the first group, moderate pain (4-6 points) in 7 (13.2%), mild pain in 21 (38.2%) patients in the second group, moderate pain in 33 (60%), very severe pain (7-9 points) in one patient, unbearable pain (10 points) in one patient, mild pain in 6 (11%) patients in the third group, moderate pain in 42 (73.6%), very severe pain in 8 (14%), and unbearable pain in 1 (2%) patient.

After surgery, pain syndrome regressed to the point of disappearance in all three groups, mild pain persisted only in two patients in the first group, one patient in the second group, and four patients in the third group, which proves the effectiveness of treatment methods with a differentiated approach.

The visual scale and its five parameters allow a more detailed examination of the pain syndrome, no pain (0 points), mild pain (1-3 points), moderate pain (4-6 points), very severe pain (7-9 points), unbearable pain (10 points), which means the maximum possible version of the sensation of pain syndrome.

Thus, the restriction of movement, the inability of patients to engage in everyday work sharply reduces social existence and adaptation in the living environment. A long process of rehabilitation and pain syndrome exhausts the nervous system in most patients, causing emotional even after the disorder and depressive syndrome, which persists for a long time even after recovery.

Conclusions:

1. Distribution of patients by age and gender showed that among the patients, men predominated, there were 116 (70.2%), and women - 49 (29.8%), which is associated with the physical exertion of men during work. The majority of patients 68 (41.5%) were of middle and old age, the maximum number of patients fell on the age group 60-74 years, 50 (30.4%), which is consistent with the data of world scientists.

2. Analysis of the level of damage to the roots of the equine tail in the studied 165 patients showed the following results, twice as many observations at the level of LV-SI 106 (64.3%) compared to LIV-LV 59 (35.7%), this is due to the greatest load on the lumbar spine associated with a low-mobility sacrum

3. When examining the somatic status, it was revealed that among 165 patients, 67 (40.5%) patients had somatic pathology, manifested in the form of arterial hypertension in 51 (31.0%) patients, ischemic heart disease in 13 patients (7.8%). In 18 (11.2%) observations, diabetes mellitus was noted, in 4 (2.6%) patients, liver pathology, and in 1 (0.9%), renal failure.

4. In our study, 112 (67.8%) of 165 patients underwent surgical treatment. The indications for surgical treatment were: cauda equina syndrome with increasing dysfunction of the pelvic organs and radiculo-ischemic manifestations; duration of radicular pain syndrome or pain in the lumbar region for at least 4 weeks; herniated intervertebral disc of any localization, but only at one level, confirmed by MRI with axial sections; lack of effect from conservative treatment.

5. The most frequent complaint presented by patients in the second and third groups was pain in the lumbar spine 38 cases, the second most frequent complaint was gait disturbance and sensory impairment 36 cases each, the third most common complaint was a forced body position due to pain syndrome 27 cases.

6. Positive results among the 165 patients studied were noted in 156 (95.6%), without changes in 9 (5.4%). The indicators in all three groups were good, since a differentiated approach to the treatment of patients with lumbar pain is always justified.

7. The VAS scores before surgery revealed mild pain (1-3 points) in 20 (37.7%) patients in the first group, moderate pain (4-6 points) in 7 (13.2%), mild pain in 21 (38.2%) patients in the second group, moderate pain in 33 (60%), very severe pain (7-9 points) in one patient, unbearable pain (10 points) in one patient, and mild pain in 6 (11%) patients in the third group, moderate pain in 42 (73.6%), very severe pain in 8 (14%), and unbearable pain in 1 (2%) patient.

8. A study of 165 patients showed that the QOL parameters that suffer the most are pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression, which is facilitated by the emotional state of patients.

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